

PETROLOGY OF WADDINGTON BAY (KYIV PENINSULA, GRAHAM COAST OF THE ANTARCTIC PENINSULA)

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The Kyiv Peninsula (KP) forms the most notable topographical element of the mainland on the Graham Coast. Despite its proximity to the Ukrainian Antarctic Station (UAS), the KP geology remains largely unknown and requires detailed study. Geological surveys covered only a narrow strip of its western coast. Therefore, it is important to explore the bays that penetrate the KP as far as possible. Waddington Bay (WB) is located 20 km east of the UAS and is one of four bays that intersect the KP from the West. Academic literature review provided preliminary information on geological features and main rock types of WB; determination of zircon U-Pb isotope ages on granite ($117,0 \pm 0,8$ Ma), granodiorite ($84,5 \pm 0,9$ Ma), quartz diorite ($85,2 \pm 0,7$ Ma); as well as a detailed survey of WB interior and surrounding elevations. Authors in this abstract present some results of the processing of field data.

The coastline of WB is composed of igneous rocks, with granitoids being the most widespread. These granitoids are represented by granites and granodiorites, which form Mount Mill in the north, and the northern slopes of Mount Demaria in the south. The granites on the western slope of Mount Mill are pale pink, coarse- to medium-grained, with typical granitic minerals such as quartz, alkali feldspar, and plagioclase. Minor components include biotite and ore minerals, with accessory minerals such as epidote, allanite, and amphiboles. These granites also contain aplite-pegmatoid veins distinguished by their fine-grained texture, higher quartz content, and lower amounts of dark minerals such as biotite and ore minerals. At the northern coastline, cataclastic granites are observed at the contact between gabbroids and granites. These resemble the previously described granites but are more altered, containing accessory minerals like epidote, chlorite, sericite, zircon, and apatite. An outcrop of granophyre is present on the northern slope of Demaria. These rocks are middle-grained, consist mostly of quartz and feldspars, but also have a small amount of amphibole, apatite, muscovite, and chlorite.

The granodiorites near the summit of Mount Mill are light gray, medium-grained, and primarily composed of plagioclase and quartz. Minor minerals include alkali feldspar, amphibole, biotite, and ore minerals, while accessory minerals include zircon, apatite, epidote, sericite, and pelite. The granodiorites of the region are notable for the presence of mafic magmatic enclaves, appearing as small round dark-coloured inclusions composed mostly of microdiorite. Except as mentioned inclusions, microdiorites have been found on Rasmussen Island. They are light grey, fine-grained, and mainly composed of plagioclase and quartz, with minor amphiboles, both rhombic and monoclinic pyroxenes, and ore minerals.

Gabbroids are relatively widespread, occurring in the central and estuarine parts of the WB on both the northern and southern shores. They form the layered Tuxen-Rasmussen intrusion. The primary minerals in these gabbroids include plagioclase, with lesser amounts of amphibole and occasional pyroxenes. Secondary minerals include ferrotitanium oxide ores and quartz, while accessory minerals such as apatite, sphene, zircon, and baddeleyite are present. Occasionally, biotite, chlorite, and talc can also be found.

Andesites form the outer part of WB and are found near Rasmussen Hut and the northwestern slope of Mount Demaria. These dark grey andesites are holocrystalline and exhibit a porphyritic texture, where phenocrysts consist of plagioclase grains. Plagioclase is also the dominant mineral in the matrix. Secondary and accessory minerals include pyroxenes, ore minerals, muscovite, quartz, chlorite, and occasional albite grains. Volcanic glass is replaced by secondary minerals.

Described above volcanic and plutonic rocks are dissected by numerous mafic dykes. Their petrographic study is still ongoing.